

Chamunda: An Ancient Goddess and Her Enduring Legacy in Indian Tradition

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Abstract: Revered as one of the saptamatrikas, the cult of Chamunda can be traced back to terracotta seals of buffalo slaying in Indus valley. Upholding her wrathful fearsome emaciated form against all the aggressions tantric culture has ever faced, her cult played a pivotal role in shaping the theology of Mahisamardini and Kali as we know today. From a popular matrika of Vajrayana to local protecting deity of rural areas, mother's timeless journey is still ongoing in different shrines and temples throughout bengal, bestowing her compassion over us. This article is a humble attempt to elaborate the magnificent aura of that supreme mother, through our past, present and upcoming future.

Keywords: Chamunda, Charchika, Saptamatrika, Harappa, Gauda, Mahisamardini, Kali, Vajrayogini, Nrityachamunda, Nayapal, Kankaleswari, Petkati, Attahas, Nachinda, Sarbamangala.

Introduction

Salutations to Yogishwari, the wielder of the sharp sword, whose protruded tongue is eager to drink blood, with hair that rises like a flame. Her mouth full of teeth and abdomen very thin. She wears garland of skulls. She holds in her left hand a bloodied sword while in her right hand holds a severed head. Flocks of vultures and crows circle around her, as she wears a leopard skin around her waist. This is the form of Chamunda, a powerful and fearsome deity to be meditated upon, a symbol of the cosmic destruction and regeneration that she embodies.

Not any esoteric practice of Tantra in an ancient temple. Not even any special puja of any tantric in the crematorium on the dark night of new moon. Rather, the aforesaid worship of Goddess Chamunda, an ancient and formidable form of the divine, finds a prominent place at the very beginning of the Durga Puja, the prime celebration in Bengali culture. Durga Puja is not only a celebration of the divine feminine but also a commemoration of the victory of good over evil, with Chamunda playing a critical role in this cosmic battle. It is noteworthy that on the morning of Saptami, Durga Puja begins with the worship of Chamunda through this meditation, offering Him Mashkalai made of vermilion. Durga, Chandi, and Chamunda are united here. What better example could there be of the history and current tradition of Chamunda Puja, our topic?

Ancestry

Chamunda is a very ancient Matrika. A terracotta plate from the ancient Indus Valley Civilization shows goat sacrifice in front of Mother goddess, residing in an auspicious tree. The Saptamatrikas are seen to surround her receiving the sacrifice. Chamunda is one of these Saptamatrikas, whose worship remained uninterrupted even during the Puranic period, over two and a half thousand years after the decline of the Harappan civilization.

Sri Sri Chandi mentions the name Chamunda as a title of Kali due to slaying the fearsome demons Chanda and Munda. It is important to note that in Sanskrit grammar, the word "Chamunda" does not originate from the slaying of Chanda and Munda. The name likely has Dravidian rather than Sanskrit roots. During the Puranic period, the narrative of Chanda-Munda slaying was created to explain the mother's name. Similarly, in the Vamana Purana, there is an attempt to derive the etymology of Chamunda for using the skin of demon Ruru as shield and cutting the demon's head to take the skull. Even today, in the Navapatrika (collection of nine herbs and trees as a manifestation of Mother goddess) of Durga Puja, Chamunda is represented by Manakachu (*Alocasia macrorrhizos*) and Kali by Kachu (*Colocasia esculenta*). Chamunda may be neglected in central place of Puranic literature, but she has been integral to India's Matri Sadhana tradition for centuries. In Sri Sri Chandi, she is depicted as the wielder of Khatbanga, adorned with a garland of skulls; wearing tiger skins; with a slender body and immense strength. Her Karala (terrifying) face is enormous; her tongue lolls out; her eyes are round; her roar shakes the entire cosmos.

Evolution over time

Typical features of Pala era Kali idols include: a sword in the hand, a Khatbanga adorned with a skull, a garland of skulls (Mundamalini), and a fierce demeanor riding on a corpse. This concept is ancient, rooted in the Bronze Age idols of the Harappan and Zhob valley civilizations. This form of Mother goddess symbolizes the omnipresent constant flow of time. She is the guide of deads in underworld, the embodiment of cosmic principles. This traditional form of Kali manifests in extraordinary ways.

Some unique variations of early Kali idols are found in Gauda (ancient Bengal) and the Deccan. In one form, the Matrika rests a trident on her right arm and a serpent in her upper right hand, holding two severed heads in her lower hands. A Khatbanga rests on her left shoulder. She rides a lion. An equivalent form is also found where the Matrika is seated on a corpse, her face glowing with fierce laughter. She wields trident, sword, Khatbanga, and Narmunda.

Researcher Dr Tamal Dasgupta noted that Maa Kali was widely worshiped across India for a long time. During the Tantra-influenced Pala Empire in Gaudabanga, her worship spread extensively. The current form of her image, often attributed to Krishnananda Agambagish, a prominent tantric scholar of 16th-17th century, actually predates him by at least four centuries. References to her form, described by Naropa during the Sahaj movement, suggest she was linked to Vajrayogini or Narodakini. This form, however, did not get to become the standardized version in southern India. Because the cultural tie up between two areas, unified by Pala and Sena dynasty, got severed due to Bengal's turbulent history throughout the Middle age.

During the Pala era, Chamunda's iconography became associated with two intertwined practices: Chamunda and Charchika worship. Pala-era Chamunda idols align with the description in Sri Sri Chandi. A corpse is often depicted as her vehicle, but by the end of the Pala era, this corpse began taking the form of Shiva.

Evidence of Charchika merging with Chamunda includes her forms sharing common features: lean body, garland of heads, protruding tongue and a Shava or Vetala as a vehicle. Her hairs running like flames above (similar description also seen in Vajrayana), with sparkling eyes peeping through the deep orbits like some brilliant star amidst cosmos.

The Agnipurana describes her holding human skull and Pattisha in her left hands, Kartri and Shool in her south hands. Skandapurana and Kriyakandabaridi also gives very much similar description. Skandapurana mentions an additional feature of pyre ash or bibhuti decorating her whole body.

Agnipurana has enisted the eight most notable forms of Chamunda, collectively known as Ashtamatrikas (8 forms of Ambika, the prime mother). They are Rudracharchika, Rudrachamunda, Siddhachamunda, Siddhayogeswari, Mahalaxmi, Rupvidya, Kshama and Dantura. Among them, Siddhayogeswari or Yogeswari is still worshipped in Durgapuja which we have discussed at the beginning.

The word "Charchika" is associated with the tongue (a synonym being Charcha), perhaps reflecting indigenous etymological root. In the Vedic age, the fierce form of Matrika was symbolized by fire's seven consuming flames. This ancient association persists in Charchika's fiery essence, linking her to the earliest forms of Kali worship.

Chamunda and Charchika are often described in dancing posture. In this depiction, the prime mother, riding the Vetala or undead corpses, dances as Nrityachamunda or Nrityacharchika. Dakini Yogini, Yaksha, Bhairava and her vast attendants join the cosmic dance. Notably, even today, Ghagarburi and Dhakeswari, two very ancient goddesses of Bengal are traditionally thought to resonate with the rhythms of war music (Ghagar, and Dhak). She is the source of both fine arts and valor. Her dance symbolizes the cosmic order and the cycle of creation, destruction, and renewal.

In Bengal's Bratakatha, we encounter Natai Chandi, possibly linked to Nrityachamunda described above. As we can see through literatures, these names – Chamunda, Kalratri, Chandi, Bhairavi became umbrella terms to encompass different forms of the same Mother goddess, revered across traditions. Hence dancing charchika became unified with Chandi to be later called upon as Natai chandi.

Although corpse or undeads (vetala) are her established vahana, Pechkavahini Chamunda idols (riding on an owl) are available. This probably unifies her with the goddess of wealth, Mahalaxmi, signifying the non-dual nature of Mother goddess. Chamunda statue seated on a tree was found in Rajshahi, that can be explained as a continuation of the mother goddess of Indus valley residing on tree. Because that's where, amidst the conglomeration of seven matrikas, we find our Chamunda for the first time. Gardhavahini Chamunda (riding on an ass) was also found in Rajshahi.

The discussion of cult of Charchika will remain incomplete without the discussion of Attahas Devi, just another name of the Devi Dantura (the 8th form of Asthambikas). The idol of devi

Attahas is the goddess of two satipithas, one on the banks of Ishani river in Ketugram, Burdwan; and another in Birbhum. Attahas or Devi Dantura is old, seated in utkatasana (folding the knees, somewhat near squatting posture), having a wrathful smile in her face. Her body is very slender. The canines coming out of her mouth are long and fierce (that's why the name Dantura). She is seated on a lotus that rests on a chariot surrounded with an army of fox. Although not explicitly stated in the Agni Purana, this Dantura form of Charchika Devi is clearly associated with the Mahavidya Dhumavati. Dhumavati's old slender form, apparent fearsomeness, Kakadhvaja chariot find very much similarities with devi Dantura.

The ultimate development

The concept of Charchika in the Pala era was not limited to the manifestation of time or the destroyer of evil. She is the universal mother, whose devotion makes the world ecstatic. The Charchastava by the Pala era poet Sridhar (court poet of King Nayapala) is an excellent example of this. It states:

"Hail the mother, whose feet rests on the rows of all the Devas, the Asuras, and the mankind;

May her glittering foot-dust destroy all the evils of the world.

She who, after devouring the entire world, is anxious to drink the the seven seas held in her palm of her in apocalypse be praised.

After the Deluge; Bidhata, the creator godhead collects her foot dust to rebuild the new cosmos.

May that mother's one glimpse triumph over all our obstacles.

Pala emperors Mahendrapala and Nayapala were worshipers of Charchika. Nayapala's Bangarh copper reign began with the victorious sound of "Namascharchikayi. (Hail mother Charchika)"

Researcher Dr Tamal Dasgupta suggested about a possible link between Kankalitala, a famous satipeeth and Pala emperor Nayapala. Nayapala fought a devastating battle with King Laxmikarna, the ruler of Chedi kinhdom. Nayapala emerged victorious, as evidenced by the Sian Inscription (deciphered by Dinesh Sarkar), discovered in the Sian village near Bolpur. A long list of matripiths is available from this Sian text; Matripiths which were established or restored by Nayapala. From this, we can also know about the shrines of devi Charchika throughout the ancient Bengal suggesting a widespread popularity of this esoteric cult.

Charchika or Chamunda is still worshipped as Petkati (indicating her lean belly) Kankalini, and Kankaleshwari (owing to her skeletal appearance) in various places. Haraprasad Shastri noted that Kankalini Sadhana was widespread in Pala Yuga India. Twenty-four Kankalini Peethas were established across the subcontinent during this period, with Kankalitala in Birbhum serving as the principal Peetha. It was here that Shastri Mahasaya discovered an idol of Attahas Devi.

Literary evidence

By the time Saduktikarnamrita was compiled, the goddess Charchika, or Charcha, was confined to the same framework as Kali. Umapatidhar, the famous court poet of Sena dynasty, saw the boundlessness of the underworld in the eyes of Charchika, the void of the waterless sea in her

thin belly, and the collapse of demonic power in the fragmented body parts stuck in her blood-stained teeth, revealed as she smiles with love.

This form has been described by Sasibhushan Dasgupta as the manifestation of destruction. But noteworthy enough, even in this form, her ultimate compassion towards the world is revealed. Umapatidhar has seen this compassion in her smile. We can find a similar depiction of wrath and compassion in Sakta padavali of Sadhak Kamalakanta and Ramprasad.

Charchika's ferocious appearance is also described in two other verses of the Saduktikarnamrita with same amalgamation of wrath and compassion. Another verse, composed by Shatananda Kabi says,

"Oh Charchika! May your frowning eyes triumph, while crushing the bones of the Asuras with your teeth. Your wrath strikes the world during deluge as the thunderbolt of death strikes an age old mountain. Yet the cosmos resonates with your ultimate dance of death, just like an ecstatic peacock with advent of Monsoon.

Surviving tradition of worshipping Chamunda

Now we'll look into the surviving tradition of worshipping devi Chamunda in different parts of Bengal.

Petkati maa

As mentioned earlier, Chamunda is still worshipped as Petkati ma in Maynaguri, under Jalpaiguri district. The entire territory of North Bengal north of the ancient Karatoa River belonged to Pundravardhana in ancient times. Bangarh and Mahasthangarh were the two main cities of that Pundravardhana. This Petkati Devi temple near Mainaguri in Jalpaiguri district also belonged to ancient Pundravardhana. Incidentally, according to prominent historian Nihar Ranjan Roy, the Kamboja Pala kings ruled North Bengal as subordinates under Pala dynasty since the time of Devapala. It was probably when Devapala extended the Pala empire to the Himalayas that these Kamboja people came into contact with the Pala dynasty. They ruled as an independent dynasty during the period of weakness of the Pala Empire and had their capital at Priyangu, as mentioned in the Irda Copper plate. During the reign of Mahipala and Nayapala, they probably rejoined the Pala Empire. But it is undeniable that they shared the same cultural heritage with the Palas and that of ancient Bengali people. Possibly the foundation of this Petkati Charchika Devi was one of their legacies.

The idol of devi Charchika here is carved in stone, about seven feet tall. Her face is fierce, body extremely lean. Hairs burning like fire. Garland of severed heads decorate her neck, with ornaments of snake all over her body. She has ten hands. Eight of them are intact till now. Two hands on both side hold the skin of elephant. The remaining hands hold bell, skull and khatbanga in left and damaru, trident and tarjani mudra (a sign of alertness) in right respectively. Below the feet is a female figure (possibly devotee), fox and owl. A special feature of the mother's idol is a scorpion painted on the very thin belly that signify her eternal hunger to devour all evil.

The fact that the idol was found completely intact during excavation deep in the adjacent pond suggests that it survived the brutal destruction brought during Turkish invasion. According to Minhaj's account, Bakhtiyar Khilji invaded North Bengal during the Tibetan

campaign and Devikot in Pundra was his military capital. It is probably at that time that the idol was removed from its original shrine for safety and buried in the depths of this pond.

Chamunda puja

Chamunda Puja is still practiced in Hili of North Dinajpur. People of the Mahishya, Vaishya and Tili communities participate in this festival. This pooja is performed with great pomp on the first Saturday after the new moon in the month of Jaisthya. During the three days of Puja, various rituals are performed. Devotees, clad in white dhoti, each holding a bamboo stick about three and a half hands long, sing and dance from house to house with traditional instruments. They bring a large and a small wooden mask (mukha) of Goddess Chamunda from the shrine. The chief devotee wears the large mukha and sing about devi Chamunda. The rest sing and dance around the small mukha.

After this ceremony takes place for a long night, the large mukha of Chamunda is kept in the temple premises and the small mukha is placed under a tree in the forest outside the locality. The next day the worshiper performs puja for two to three hours with sandesh, mango, jackfruit, banana etc brought by devotees. A fair is held for three days on the occasion of Puja. The main attraction of the fair is the sale of various iron products.

Legend has it that two hundred years ago, a local landlord's elephant got stuck in the mud while bathing in the nearby Yamuna river. The zamindar dreamt that Goddess Chamunda has manifested herself between two rocks at a certain place in the river. The next day the zamindar went and found a part of a neem tree stuck between the stones at the right place. From that piece of wood he established the goddess by making a mask of the goddess. The mantra of awakening Chamunda Devi of Hilli with the collective singing of devotees to the rhythm of Dhak and Kanshi music is still alive among the local people.

Today's Dinajpur was once the capital of Pala dynasty. Even today we can get a glimpse of the mother goddess worshipping tradition till intact in their original form since Pala era. This Chamunda Puja is a beautiful example of that.

Charchika of Shibbari

Siddhacharchika or Siddhachamunda of Pala era is still worshiped in Shibbari village of South Dinajpur. She is ten armed, holding tarjani mudra, khatbanga, severed head, skull, sword, shield, damaru, scythe, Shul and Bhakshamudra (suggesting engulfing the evil). On both sides are dancing Dakini Yogini. The goddess herself is dancing standing on the shoulder of a betal.

Chamunda of Manteswar

Monteshwar in the Burdwan district was originally known as Mantreshwar (a school of Mantrayana), a major center of Tantric practices. Maa Chamunda has been worshipped here for the past 900 years. The goddess has eight hands and holds a damru, shul, sword and a drinking pot in her right hands, while her left hands hold a trishul, khatvanga, severed head and tarjani mudra. With hair resembling flames, and fearsome eyes, the mother dances over a corpse, flanked by two attendant Dakini and Yogini on either side.

Every year, during the Shukla Paksha of the month of Boishakh, countless devotees gather for a five-day celebration of Mother Chamunda's worship and a grand fair. This puja holds as much significance here as Durga Puja does elsewhere. Radical scholars, who unnecessarily

associate the eternal rituals of sharadiya Durgapuja with mythical heroes, should make a note of this.

Chamunda puja officially commences on Akshaya Tritiya in Boishakh with the traditional peacock dance, similar to the dance observed at the Yogadya Peeth in Kshirgram, Burdwan. According to researcher Tamal Dasgupta, this tradition has Dravidian roots linked to Bengali culture.

On the midnight of Saptami, the goddess is immersed in the adjacent pond, and the Bagdi community guards the idol throughout the night. The next day, the idol is retrieved from the water at noon. Until then, the villagers observe Arandhan (refraining from cooking in their homes). Once the idol is retrieved, rituals and sacrifices begin beside the pond itself. The goddess is carried back to the main temple on a chaturdola (a ceremonial palanquin) while devotees perform exuberant dances. That night, after the goddess reaches the temple, buffalo and goat sacrifices are performed. On Navami, devotees take the chaturdola to various altars for pujas. Finally, on Dashami, thousands of people gather at the puja grounds to mark the culmination of the festival.

Both Yogadya and Chamunda are Peetheshwari Matrika (regional patron goddesses) of Burdwan. Their worship dates back to the Pala-Sena era, though its origins likely predate even that, reaching back to the earliest phases of Bengali civilization. Both rituals include the peacock dance and the tradition of retrieving the idol from a pond, characteristics of maternal worship seen since the Indus Valley Civilization. Researcher Tamal Dasgupta suggests that Peetheshwari Sthanamatrika, the concept of regional patron goddesses, reflects the matriarchal traditions of the subcontinent, originating in the Harappan civilization. Thus, Maa Chamunda is the godmother of Mantreshwar.

Katyayani of Telkupi

Another significant temple tied to the tradition of Maa Charchika (or Chamunda) is the Katyayani Temple in Simra village, near Telkupi in Purulia's Raghunathpur area. This temple, built in the Rekha Deul architectural style, houses Goddess Charchika/Chamunda in the sanctum sanctorum.

Telkupi, or ancient Tailakampa, belongs to Shikharbhoom and was home to many shrines of matrika built during the rule of the Shikhara kings of the Pala and Sena periods. Rudrasikhara, one of the Shikhara kings, played a significant role during the reign of Rampala to reestablish Pala rule by defeating Kaivartya king Bheema, resisting state power. The Peetha of Maa Kalyaneshwari was also established here during the Sena period. Unfortunately, many temples in Telkupi were submerged during the construction of the Panchet Reservoir, an utter loss attributed solely to government negligence.

The name Katyayani, associated with fierce yet compassionate Matrika, appears in ancient Sanskrit literature. According to the Harivamsa, the goddess was worshipped as Katyayani by forest tribes like Shabars and Pulindas. In ancient Bengal, Maa Katyayani was venerated on the banks of the Ganges as the slayer of demons Shumbha and Nishumbha, standing atop a prostrated Mahadev, with the Ganges flowing around her feet. In Tantric traditions, her vehicle is Betal, and her companions are fearsome entities, signifying her unity with Chamunda. The idol of Charchika Devi inside the sanctum sanctorum of Katyayani Temple is a Dashabhuja (ten-armed) form, dancing over a corpse with Dakini Yogini on either side.

Charchikatala of Alugram

An extinct Charchika Peeth is located in Aulgram, Murshidabad, where a n enriched Vajrayana Vihara stood during the Pala era, built around the late 8th or early 9th century. During the reign of Pala emperor Devapala, Bengal achieved pan-Indian prominence. Devpal, like his father Dharmapala, was a great patron of Tantric Buddhism, under whose reign numerous Viharas, Mahaviharas, and Sangharamas were built. The temple in Aulgram was one such site where Padmapani Avalokiteshvara and Goddess Vajracharchika of Akshavya kula were worshipped. The shrine is still known as Charchikatla, preserving the memory of that bygone tradition of worshipping Charchika Devi.

Charchikatla has gone through many ups and downs and has lost much of its past traces. However an inquisitive eye can easily pick up the clues sufficient to visualise the ancient monastery. The Bhairabnath Shiv Mandir lies on the way to Charchikatla along the main path of the village. It is reasonable to assume that this Bhairabnath temple was originally the temple of Bhairava, the gatekeeper of Charchika. In the Tantric concept, Bhairava and Kshetrapala were traditionally located at the entrance of the main shrine. This Bhairava temple, too, is situated at the junction of the main village road and Charchikatla.

A little further ahead lies a Shiva temple. housing three shiva linga Batukeshwar, Tarakeshwar, and Raghaveshwar. Another noteworthy detail is that the Dharmaraj Tagore of the village also resides in the same house as these three Shivas throughout the year. Since Vajrayani and Sahajani Buddhists once had a deep connection with Dharma Thakura, it is possible that these three Shiva temples, situated so close to the Charchika temple, were once temples dedicated to the companion gods of Vajrayana goddess Charchika. From the name Batukeshwar, it seems likely that this temple was originally a shrine to Batuk Bhairava. The Ashta Matrika (eight mother goddesses) of Tantra worship are said to have Batuk Bhairavas as their sons, and Charchika is essentially a variant of Chamunda, one of the eight Matrikas. Over time, Chamundaputra Batuk Bhairava likely took the form of Batukeshwar Shiva.

Beyond these three Shiva temples lies the present temple of Charchika. It houses the footstage of the ancient Charchika idol, along with the remnants of the pillars of the ancient Vihara. On the pedestal, one can see depictions of Brahma, Vishnu, and Mahesh. This seems to express the idea of Charchika as the primal mother, who resides above all the gods.

Sarvamangala of Jajan

Now let's look into the temple of Devi Sarvamangala in Jajan, an ancient village of Murshidabad. Jajan was once known as Jayayan. It is unclear whether its connection lies with Jainag or Shashankadev, the ruler of Gaur. According to Nagendranath Basu Mahashay, Jayayan was strategically situated as the main tax collection center of Uttara Raha, bordered by the rivers Mayurakshi in the north, Ajay in the south, Bhagirathi in the east, and Dwarka in the west.

After the death of Vighrapala in the Pala era, this Jayayan region briefly came under the control of the Burman dynasty of Bengal during the Kaivarta rule. In AD 778, a merchant named Rameshwar Datta, resident of Bodpur (past name probably Baidyapur), a village near Jayayan, established the idol and temple of Goddess Sarvamangala at Devipur near Bodpur.

This information is available from an inscription found in the temple. He also referred to himself as a descendant of Chand Banik, the famous mythological merchant mentioned in the story of snake Goddess Manasa. Goddess Sarvamangala is the presiding deity of Jajan. Originally the idol of the goddess was that of devi Chamunda, dancing over the corpse; slender body; fierce look and garland of skull. Later in times of political turmoil, the idol was immersed in the pond behind the temple. Later, during mid time of Pala era, this area was ruled by Soma Ghosh, who came from Kolanch, Mithila and settled in this Jayayan village near Mayurakshi. He received a dream and rescued the idol of Sarvamangala Maa Charchika from the pond behind the temple. Many consider this Soma Ghosh to be the ancestor of Ishai Ghosh, the lord of Ajeya Dhekkari, another mythological warrior described in Dharmamangal.

Later, Sarvamangala Charchika idol disappeared from the time of Turkish invasion. Since then Goddess Sarvamangala has been worshiped in the form of an aniconic stone. Some say the fragmented remains of the main idol is kept covered in the sanctum sanctorum. In the month of Baisakh, the idol is taken out for a day and circumambulated. The daily service of the goddess is done by serving fish. Parts of the pillars and arches of the Pala and Sen age are still visible in the present temple.

Nachinda of Midnapore

The famous shrine of Ma Nachinda of East Medinipur is associated with this temple are four forms of Mother goddess. Chandi, Sheetala, Shasthi, Mansa. The four matrikas of the Nachinda temple probably constituted an ancient mandala of tantras. Three, four, five or seven matrikara mandals have been in use since the time of the Indus civilization. Even today, Maa Sheetala is worshiped in most places in the sect of seven sisters. The same happened in Nachinda temple.

Nrityaratha or dancing Rudrachamunda was worshipped in tantric cults of Pala era as the prime mother; as dark as a cloud, three eyed, naked, with a garland of skulls around her neck, dancing over corpse or shiva under his feet. She is called Nateshwari in this stanza, meaning that she was worshiped in the theaters and musical schools of that era. It is not impossible for Maa Nachinda of Medinipur district to carry the memory of Nritya Chamunda, so far the etymological root is concerned.

Atbaichandi of Indpur, Bankura

The word Chandi signifies the vast principle of the World Mother. In whatever form the Mother destroys the forces of evil and manifests in the devotee's heart as the giver of fearlessness, all those forms are known as Chandi. Thus, Mangala Chandi, Durga, Kali, Chamunda—even the formless Supreme Prakriti, the cosmic cause beyond speech and mind—are all described as Chandi.

In the imagination of the poet Bhavabhuti, she is the deity worshiped by the forest-dwelling Shabar tribes. She devours demons with her army of spirits. Her crimson feet are anointed by the sacred Ganga flowing from Shiva's matted locks.

Even today, in Chaurabaid village under Indpur police station in Bankura, Mother Chamunda is worshiped as Atbaichandi. Due to natural decay over centuries, the image of the goddess has become indistinct. Yet it is evident that she represents the ten-armed Siddha Chamunda or Siddha Charchika of the Pala period. In her hands she holds the gesture of warning, a khatvanga (skull-staff), human skull, severed head, sword, shield, drum, sickle, spear, and the gesture of

devouring. On either side stand dancing dakinis and yoginis. The goddess herself dances while standing upon the shoulder of a spirit.

This region of Bankura was once covered with dense forests. The fierce Nishadas and Shabar tribes here practiced mother worship, as is also known from ancient Sanskrit literature. The name Atbaichandi must have come from the name Aranyachandi or Atavichandi, Goddess of the forest.

The idol of maa Atbaichandi now remains under the open sky. In Chaurabaid village the ruins of an ancient Pala-Sena temple still exist, perhaps where the goddess was once worshiped. The stone image of the Mother is three and a half feet tall, carved out of a slab of black stone. The presence of an amalaka (temple finial) kept beside the idol suggests that a temple once stood here.

According to local tradition, this Chandi Peeth was the original shrine of Mother Bashuli. Later, the shrine of Bashulichandi, worshiped by the poet Chandidas, was transferred at Chhatna. It appears that the worshippers of Bashuli were once also connected with the practices of Chamunda worship. It is perhaps because of the influence of cult of maa Siddhachamunda, that blended within the cult of Bashuli. May be this is where the true significance of Chandidas's name lies.

Gambhira dance of Maldah

Gambhira festival of Bachamari in Malda is another traditional sign of Chamunda matrikara sadhana.

Maldah district belongs to the ancient Pundravardhan region. Even in some period of Pala and Sena era, Gauda, the center of Bengali political-cultural identity of that era was also located in this district. That the ancient customs and rituals of mother goddess worshipping tradition, admixed with several vestiges of its modern life is surviving and is still alive, despite many setbacks.

It is well known that ancient practices of Tantra are expressed in Gambhira Utsav Ekadhar. On either side of the Bachamari area are two main Matrikara temples, Ma Chamunda and Ma Burikali, revered as two sisters. The 'Mukha' of the mother from the two temples are brought at one place. Devotees believe that the two sisters meet at the same place only once a year. Matrikas are brought in a procession accompanied by masked devotees dancing and singing. At that moment, the the artists wearing the mother's mask are considered the manifestation of the mother herself.

Gambhira Utsav begins every year at the beginning of a new Bangla year. Dance with burning torch, mask dance and procession continues throughout the night until next morning. This Gambhira dance is a beautiful manifestation of tantric celebration that originated in Chamunda worshipping cult.

Kankaleshwari Kali of Bardhaman: Rudracharchika

Researcher Dr Tamal Dasgupta has noted that although the temple itself is not ancient, the idol of Mother Kankaleshwari is at least a thousand years old. Her form is undoubtedly that of maa Rudracharchika from the Pala-Sena period. During both the Pala and Sena eras, her cult was at the peak of popularity. She is depicted as fleshless, with the skeletal structure prominently

displayed. Indeed, it is said of the Kankaleshwari image that her bones and veins are rendered with remarkable precision.

This idol in Kanchannagar, Bardhaman, is said to have been washed ashore at Chaudhuri-daha in the Damodar river flood of 1320 Bengali Era (c. 1913 CE), lying face down. Thus, it was perceived only as a stone slab, and the washermen used the reverse side of this six-foot basalt stone for beating clothes. In 1323 Bengali Era (c. 1916 CE), when an earthquake caused cracks in Chaudhuri-daha, the stone overturned, revealing its front, and the image was discovered. In that same year, under the initiative of the Bardhaman royal family, the idol was enshrined in a Pancharatna (five-spired) temple.

Kankaleswari, in her Rudra Chamunda form, is eight-armed (Ashtabhuj). Of her eight hands, the four on the right hold a sword, a damaru, a trident, and a skull-bowl. In the four on the left she bears a harvesting weapon much like the scythe carried by the Grim Reaper in the Western world, a bell, a severed head, and the gesture of devouring (bhakshana mudra). On either side stand her two attendants, while beneath her feet she tramples the corpse of Shiva (Shava-Shiva).

In her dhyana mantra, she is described as holding a damaru and a severed head, and she is referred to as Nrityeshwari. Indeed, she was a tutelary goddess in the dance, music, and theatrical traditions of the ancient urban culture of Bengal.

Conclusion

This is how Chamunda or Charchika are still worshiped in different parts of Bengal. Sometimes in her own name, sometimes as Kali. Ever the Lokayat dance, the mantra of Mahapuja has retained the indication of his pursuit. He is still relevant in the Bengali consciousness from the time of the Indus Civilization through the glorious chapters of the Pala and Sena era.

The Kankaleshwari Kali of Burdwan is another shrine where Rudracharchika idol of the Pala era, is worshipped till date. Although the original temple housing is abolished, the idol survived the brutal invasions of Middle age.

The idol in Burdwan's Kanchannagar is said to have floated to a Chowdhury family during a Damodar River flood in 1917. As the idol appeared like a block of stone, washermen used the back of the six-foot basalt statue to beat clothes. Some years later, an earthquake caused a crack in the stone, it overturned, revealing the idol's front, leading to its discovery. The idol was then installed in a Pancharatna temple that same year, under the initiative of the Bardhaman Raj.

This idol, Rudracharchika or Rudrachamunda, is eight-armed (a similar ten-armed figure is called Siddhacharchika or Siddhachamunda). In her right hands, she holds a sword, damru, trident, and kapal-patra. In her left hands, she holds a scythe (resembling the Grim Reaper's weapon in Western tradition), bells, narmunda, and coins. Two attendants flank the goddess, who dances over chanting devotees at her feet. She was the matriarch of dance and theatrics in Bengal's ancient civilization.

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